

Remote-Assisted Real-Time Car Operating System

N. Nagasuresh Babu ^{*1}, Darshan B S ², Nithish Kumar M S ³, Omkar Kalekar ⁴, Yuvraj Kharde ⁵

1 – Senior Assistant Professor, REVA University

2,3,4,5 – UG Students, REVA University

ABSTRACT

Conventional crash testing methods often fall short in accurately simulating real-world scenarios and delivering practical results. These methods typically involve pulling the chassis of the car, which fails to replicate dynamic driving conditions effectively. To address this challenge, our study proposes a novel approach: an Arduino-based remote-assisted real-time car operating system (OS). This innovative system seamlessly integrates with various vehicles, leveraging Arduino's robust control capabilities to interface directly with a car's steering, acceleration, and braking mechanisms through dedicated motor driver circuits. By maintaining engine functionality and granting access to acceleration, braking, and steering, our system enables precise control in special conditions such as curves and sudden braking, thereby enhancing the accuracy and relevance of crash test simulations. Utilizing Bluetooth connectivity, the system translates remote control commands into real-time car actions, facilitated by Arduino's processing power. This enables the development of advanced remote-control interfaces prioritizing user experience and intuitive control. Through meticulous design, rigorous implementation, and thorough validation procedures, our project aims to achieve significant improvements in vehicle manoeuvrability, safety, and overall user experience. By addressing critical challenges in the automotive safety testing domain, our technology offers a transformative solution for conventional crash testing methods, providing more practical results and insights into vehicle safety performance.

Keywords: Crash testing, Chassis, Dynamic driving conditions, Arduino-based, Steering, Bluetooth connectivity.

1. Introduction

In an era marked by rapid technological progress, the automotive industry spearheads innovation, striving for safer, more efficient, and versatile vehicles that reshape transportation norms. At the forefront of this evolution is the quest for advanced vehicle control systems, aimed at enhancing safety and redefining driving experiences. Within this context emerges a novel approach—a remote-assisted real-time car operating system—poised to revolutionize vehicular control dynamics.

The core objective of this endeavour is to develop a sophisticated and adaptable system capable of seamlessly integrating with diverse vehicle models. Central to this vision lies the empowerment of drivers with unprecedented control over steering, acceleration, and braking mechanisms, facilitated by advanced electrical actuators. Leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as Bluetooth connectivity and Arduino

microcomputers, this system redefines vehicle control boundaries, offering a comprehensive suite of functionalities tailored to modern driving needs.

Beyond hardware integration, this solution embodies a holistic approach to vehicle control, encompassing advanced remote-control interfaces designed to empower users with intuitive and responsive interaction capabilities. Moreover, this technology finds practical applications in crash testing, offering more realistic and insightful results compared to conventional methods. By maintaining engine functionality and enabling precise control, it enhances the accuracy and relevance of crash test simulations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Weicheng Zhang, et.al, discuss a study focused on transitioning one type of wheel engineering vehicle from manual control to remote control. The study systematically analyzes the operating schematic of the hydraulic system belonging to this type of vehicle. It also characterizes the manual control process. An overall plan of the electro-hydraulic remote proportional control system is introduced. The hydraulic oil circuit of the controlling part is established. The converted wheel vehicle is presented. The new vehicle is designed to meet the requirements of practical application, indicating successful development and implementation of the remote-control system. [1]

Y. Yu and S. Lee, et. al, the paper presents a comprehensive exploration of the impact of communication methods and vehicle speed on remote driving performance, using ROS as the core architecture. It highlights the significance of real-time data transmission for effective remote control of vehicles. The findings underscore the superiority of UDP-based video streaming for remote driving, especially in low-speed environments, due to its low latency. This research lays a solid foundation for future advancements in autonomous driving technology by bridging the gap between current AI-based systems and fully autonomous vehicles. [2]

Lei Kang, Wei Zhao, Bozhao Qi et.al, suggests a third alternative for dealing with occasional failures in self-driving vehicles: returning control to remote human drivers in response centers. This approach aims to address challenges such as unfamiliar situations or conflicting data. However, it highlights the need for robust communication infrastructure and Quality of Service guarantees to ensure efficient remote driver response. The study's focus on real-time streaming testbeds and latency evaluation reflects a practical

approach to understanding these challenges and optimizing solutions. Overall, it underscores the complexity of integrating remote human control into autonomous vehicle systems while emphasizing the potential for innovative communication infrastructure designs to support this approach. [3]

M. S. Srikanth, T. G. Keerthan Kumar, et.al, suggest the proposed model addresses the challenges of vehicle monitoring by integrating IoT, cloud computing, and machine learning technologies. IoT enables the collection of various vehicle parameters such as distance traveled, lubricant level, tire conditions, and GPS location in real time through sensors like IR, MQ 6, HC SR 04, and LDR sensors. This data is stored in the cloud for analysis. Machine learning algorithms are trained using real-time vehicle service data and GPS data to predict the vehicle's condition and suggest the next service date, reducing the need for human effort in predicting service schedules. The model utilizes previously collected data and advanced algorithms to provide efficient results. The collected data is stored in the cloud and made accessible through an Android application for both users and service providers, enhancing convenience and enabling proactive maintenance and security measures during travel.[4]

Damian Freja and Marek Jaśkiewicz, et.al, study focused on presents a test stand equipped with a control system and data acquisition for conducting experimental crash tests at low speeds. These tests focus on the impact of low-speed collisions on wheelchairs and seats. The measurement equipment allows for the recording and analysis of displacements in various parts of the body of the tested object.

During the tests, a constant speed of 20 km/h is maintained, and the study includes volunteers of both genders. The research results indicate that the trajectory of head movement for female volunteers aligns closely with that of male volunteers. This finding suggests that gender differences in head movement during low-speed crashes may not be significant.

The implications of these findings are crucial for the construction of anthropometric dummies intended for low-speed crash tests. By demonstrating that head movement trajectories are similar across genders, the study supports the use of anthropometric dummies that represent the average population without the need for gender-specific models. This simplifies testing procedures and ensures that crash test results can be generalized across different demographic groups.[5]

3. Objectives

1. Develop a specialized operating system for remote-assisted crash testing in vehicles, ensuring compatibility with various car models and precise control over steering, acceleration, and braking

functions.

2. Streamline the integration of DC motors and actuators into existing vehicle systems, minimizing complexity and ensuring compatibility through comprehensive testing and validation of integrated components.

4. Methodology:

Conducting a comprehensive Literature Survey involved analysing existing research to discern trends, technologies, and methodologies relevant to remote-assisted car operating systems. This process included examining academic papers, industry reports, and patents to gain insights into prior endeavours, technological advancements, and potential challenges. Leveraging this knowledge, Remote Operating System Design focused on developing a specialized system tailored for car operations, integrating Arduino microcontrollers and Bluetooth connectivity. The system architecture ensured compatibility with various car models while enabling precise control over steering, acceleration, and braking functions. Components Selection involved meticulously curating hardware components, considering factors like reliability, performance, and compatibility to streamline system integration. Strategies were devised to seamlessly incorporate Internet of Things (IoT) technology into hardware systems, enhancing connectivity and data exchange capabilities. Bluetooth Interface App Selection involved assessing available options to identify a suitable interface for remote control. Performance Evaluation rigorously tested system performance, reliability, and responsiveness under various conditions. Through meticulous Debugging and Analysis, issues were identified and resolved to enhance system stability and functionality. Finally, Conclusion and Recommendations synthesized findings, outlining implications, and suggesting avenues for future research and development.

Fig 1: Methodology

5. DESIGN OF OPERTING SYSTEM

5.1 Introduction

The Remote-Assisted Car Operation System represents a significant advancement in automotive technology, leveraging Bluetooth connectivity and Arduino microcomputers to enable remote control functionalities. This innovative system is designed to enhance user convenience, safety, and overall driving experience. By allowing users to remotely operate critical functions of the vehicle, such as steering, acceleration, and braking, the system opens new possibilities for vehicle control and automation.

5.2 Fabrication of Operating system:

Component Selection: Choose appropriate hardware components such as Arduino microcontrollers, Bluetooth modules, H-bridges, relays, power supply units, DC motors, LCD displays, and necessary electronic components based on project requirements and specifications.

Circuiting: Design and assemble circuits to connect and interface electronic components. This includes creating circuits for Arduino microcontrollers, Bluetooth modules, H-bridges, relays, power supply units, and other peripheral devices. Ensure proper wiring and connections to facilitate seamless communication and functionality.

Programming: Develop Arduino sketches (code) to program the microcontroller for desired functionality. Write code to establish Bluetooth communication, control motor operations, display information on the LCD display, and handle any other system tasks. Test and debug the code to ensure proper functionality and reliability.

5.3 Program:

```
include<LiquidCrystal.h>
int rs=8,en=9,d4=10,d5=11,d6=12,d7=13;
LiquidCrystal lcd(rs,en,d4,d5,d6,d7);
#include<SoftwareSerial.h>
```

SoftwareSerial Serial1(6,7);

int relay1=14;

int relay2=15;

int relay3=16;

int relay4=17;

int m1=2;

int m2=3;

int m3=5;

int m4=4;

Mechanical Frame Building: Construct a mechanical frame or prototype of the car cabin to replicate the steering, acceleration, and braking mechanisms. Utilize materials such as wood, plastic, or metal to build a sturdy and functional frame that can withstand mechanical stress and accommodate motorized components.

Integrating Mechanical Frame with Motors and IoT Setup: Mount DC motors onto the mechanical frame in positions corresponding to the steering, acceleration, and braking mechanisms. Ensure proper alignment and secure attachment to facilitate smooth operation. Connect the DC motors to the H-bridge motor drivers and Arduino microcontroller according to the circuit design. Verify electrical connections and test motor functionality to ensure correct operation. Integrate the IoT setup, including Bluetooth modules, relays, and other electronic components, into the mechanical frame. Position components strategically for easy access and optimal performance. Establish communication between the Arduino microcontroller and the Bluetooth module to enable remote control and monitoring of the vehicle system. Test the integrated system to verify functionality and address any issues or discrepancies. Conduct thorough testing to ensure proper operation of motorized components, IoT features, and overall system performance.

Final Testing and Calibration: Conduct comprehensive testing of the entire system to validate functionality and performance. Test remote control capabilities, motor responsiveness, Bluetooth communication, and other system features. Calibrate motor operations, including steering angles, acceleration rates, and braking responsiveness, to achieve desired performance characteristics and ensure smooth operation. Address any

issues or discrepancies identified during testing and make necessary adjustments to optimize system performance and reliability.

5.4 Product Testing:

The system encompasses two primary motor groups: motors A and S, allocated for acceleration and steering, respectively, under the governance of 4-channel relays. Conversely, motors B and P manage braking and pedal movement, respectively, regulated by H-bridges. Operational commands are transmitted via a Bluetooth module, orchestrated by a compatible smartphone application. For instance, commands such as "A" initiate acceleration and forward pedal movement, while "B" triggers braking and backward pedal movement. Similarly, commands "L" and "R" direct left and right steering movements, respectively.

In addition to system development, comprehensive product testing was undertaken to assess responsiveness and operational delays across various scenarios. Each test involved transmitting commands ("A," "B," "L," and "R") from the smartphone application to the Arduino system and recording the time required for the corresponding motor actions. To ensure robustness and accuracy, these tests were replicated ten times for each command, facilitating reliable evaluation and validation of system performance.

5.5 Product Testing: Motor Operation

5.5.1 Delay Test Setup:

Mobile Device: Used to send instructions (A, B, R, L) via Bluetooth to the Arduino.

Arduino: Receives instructions from the mobile device and controls the motors accordingly.

Motors: A, B, S, P motors controlled by the Arduino through relay and H-bridge circuits.

5.5.2 Testing Procedure:

Acceleration (A) Test:

Instruction: Send command 'A' via Bluetooth.

Measure the time taken for motor A to start accelerating.

Record the delay in seconds for 10 trials.

Braking (B) Test:

Instruction: Send command 'B' via Bluetooth.

Measure the time taken for motor B to start applying brakes.

Record the delay in seconds for 10 trials.

Right Turn (R) Test:

Instruction: Send command 'R' via Bluetooth.

Measure the time taken for motor S to turn right.

Record the delay in seconds for 10 trials.

Left Turn (L) Test:

Instruction: Send command 'L' via Bluetooth.

Measure the time taken for motor S to turn left.

Record the delay in seconds for 10 trials.

Table 1: Maneuverability test results

Average Time Taken in seconds				
Command	A(Acceleration)	B (Braking)	L (Left Turn)	R (Right Turn)
Trial 1	2.14	2.37	0.99	0.98
Trial 2	2.23	2.42	0.98	0.97
Trial 3	2.2	2.01	1.00	0.99
Trial 4	2.06	2.19	0.99	0.96
Trial 5	2.09	2.44	0.99	0.98
Trial 6	2.33	2.27	0.98	0.97
Trial 7	2.29	2.03	1.00	0.99
Trial 8	2.11	2.31	0.96	0.96
Trial 9	2.16	2.18	0.99	0.96
Trial 10	2.07	2.4	0.99	0.98
Average Time (seconds)	2.16	2.24	0.98	0.97

Components of Remote Operation System - Arduino Microcomputers, Bluetooth module, H Bridge, 4-Channel Relay, Power Supply Unit, Motors, LCD Display.

Fig.1 Operating System

Fig.2 Prototype Frame

6 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the project has yielded a specialized remote-assisted real-time car operating system tailored for crash testing applications. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as Bluetooth, Arduino microcontrollers, and advanced remote-control interfaces, the system enables precise and responsive control. Its compatibility with any car model facilitates the integration of electrical actuators for steering, acceleration, and braking functions during crash simulations. This promises significant advancements in automotive safety testing, providing researchers and engineers with a reliable tool for evaluating vehicle crashworthiness and enhancing overall safety standards.

7 REFERENCES

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